

Impact of Perceive CSR, Transformational Leadership and Perceived Organizational Support on Organizational Identification and Pro environmental Behavior of Employees in Pharmaceutical Industry of Pakistan

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Abstract

As the awareness of environmental sustainability taking place in the present time, organizations are also following this trend by influencing the behavior of their employees through different factors. In this study perceived corporate social responsibility, transformational leadership, perceived organizational support and organizational identification are used as the predictor for influencing pro environmental behavior among employees working in Pharmaceutical sector of Pakistan. Data was collected from 233 respondents working in Pharmaceutical industry of Pakistan. This study found that employees exhibit more pro-environmental behavior and becomes highly identified with their organization when perceives support from their organization also when the employee perceives that their organization is responsible toward their social environment. This study also identified that transformational leadership plays an important role in influencing pro environmental behavior and organizational identification among employees. The aim of this study is to analyze the gap that transformational leadership influences pro environmental behavior of employees through intervening role of organizational identification.

Keywords: Transformational leadership, perceived corporate social responsibility, perceived organizational support, and Organizational identification and employee pro environmental behavior

1. Introduction

In order to gain competitive advantage in today's dynamic work environment, organizations around the world are initiating to upgrade their environmental performances. Business and corporate sector taking initiatives to address environmental issues, and for that organizations are emphasizing to take the strict measures to control environmental hazards. Organizations around the globe have realized it is high time to take action in order to preserve natural environment. As discussing environmental issues, use of plastic is categorized as one of the most ominous threat to the environment because of which use of plastic bags and bottles has been prohibited in many industrial sectors across the world. When employees having better understanding of their organizations, they participate more actively and become more motivated to engage in such behavior which supports their organization. Given that, the attempt of this research study is to analyze the mechanism between perception of CSR, transformational leadership, organizational support perception and engagement of employees in pro environmental behavior with the intervention of organizational identification. CSR has been a notion, as socially responsible practices of a firm that produces better work outcomes and enables more environmental focused behavior among employees. CSR linked to the perceptions of employees and interpretations of their firm's CSR activities. Engagement in more CSR activities is one of a most common practice for any business to promote their image and status and it also improves their identity within an organization. Leaders with their leadership behaviors are considered as an important tool to provoke positive behavior among the employees in any organization. Among different styles of leadership, transformational leadership has been recognized as the most important leadership style. Transformational leaders persuade a wide variety of traditional organizational results, such as attitudes and behaviors, commitment from employee as well as improved organizational and financial performance. Also it has been evident that employee performs better when organization provide support to their employees. Organizational support translates into improved work outcomes from individuals and this will also encourages employee to engage more in environmental friendly activities. Although a lot of studies have been conducted separately to examine that perceived CSR, transformational leadership and perceived organizational support have significant and strong impact on employee behavior in any organization. The main purpose of this research study is to evaluate the effect of expected predictors on pro environmental behavior among employees working in pharmaceutical industry in Karachi, Pakistan. These predictors include perceived CSR, transformational leadership, perceived organizational support and organizational identification. This study is unique of its kind as there is no study in which perceived CSR, tfl and pos are studied together to find out their impact on organizational identification and how all these variables influences employee pro environmental behavior in pharmaceutical industry of Pakistan. Today there are around 759 pharmaceutical industrialized units in Pakistan. Pharmacy industry of Pakistan meets approximately 70% demand of finished medicine of the country. This industry of Pakistan contributes approximately 1% to the GDP annually. This industry is highly regulated industry by government of Pakistan and regulated by Coordination (NHSR&C) and Ministry of National Health Services Regulations and also by the Drug Regulatory Authority of Pakistan (DRAP). Numerous researchers have studied the impact of transformational leadership on organizational identification and how it affects pro environmental behavior of employees. So many researches are conducted on transformational

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leadership that illustrate the importance of leadership in educational sectors in Pakistan (A Zulfqar, M Valcke, G Devos, 2016) and how transformational leadership influences innovative behavior in nursing sector of Pakistan (M Masood, B Afsar, 2017). Another research by M Zareen, K Razzaq (2015), demonstrated the significance of transformational leaders for the motivation of workers in banking industry of Pakistan. However, other variables of this research have been studied in various industrial sectors of Pakistan. I Ahmed, WKW Ismail (2014) conducted a research which explained the role of perception of organizational support in educational sector of Pakistan in improving the quality of employees work outcomes. M Khaleel, S Chelliah (2017) conducted a research about how perceived corporate social responsibility effects employee behavior as well as job attitude in pharmaceutical industry in Pakistan. Research by G Shahzadi, F Qadeer (2019) was conducted in hospitality sector in Pakistan in which perceived CSR was studied with organizational identification. Research conducted by Q Tian, JL Robertson, (2019) where perceived CSR was studied with organization identification and employee pro environmental behavior in hospitality industry. H Rim, SU Yang, J Lee, (2016), explored the relationship with perceived CSR and organization identification in educational sector. Despite the plethora of researches are conducted separately on perceived CSR, transformational leadership and perception of organizational support, organizational identification and employee pro environmental behavior in different and diverse industries of Pakistan, the process through which how perceived CSR, transformational leadership, and perceived organizational support altogether influences pro environmental behavior in employees in Pharmaceutical industry remained understudied. Previously, researches have been done on most of the variables of this study in different industrial sectors of Pakistan. This research identified that no study has been done on perceived CSR, transformational leadership, perceived organizational support with organizational identification and pro environmental behavior among employees working in pharmaceutical industry.

2. Theoretical Background

The present study used theory of planned behavior (Ajzen, 1985) as an underpinning theory. According to this theory intentions directed the actions of an individual. This theory is derived from the theory of reasoned action proposed by (Ajzen & Fishbein, 1980; Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975). The main purpose of the theory of reasoned action was to explain the volitional behavior of individual (JL Hale, BJ Householder, 2002). This theory of reasoned actions exclude all the factors which are hindering the voluntary behavior of individual and the aim of this theory was to explain that behavior of any individual is derive from their intentions. Later the theory has been analyzed by so many researchers and engaged in different stages of changes and theory of planned behavior was developed. Theory of planned behavior is considered to be an extended version of theory of reasoned actions. The intentions of an individual supposed to confine those motivational factors which influence or promote their behavior. These intentions are indicators to perform a behavior to check the willingness to try and the efforts planned by individuals to exert. Or in other words stronger the intention of an individual to engage in certain behavior, the more well of its outcome or performance. Supporting theory of this study includes social identity theory (Tajfel, 1989), variables derived from this theory are perceived corporate social responsibility and organizational identification. Other than that perceived organizational support is also comes under the theory of Social identity. Transformational leadership theory (Bass, 1985) is also used as supporting theory in the present study, which explains the unique relationship between followers and their leaders that narrates exceptional performances and accomplishments for any organization.

2.1. Perceived Corporate Social Responsibility

Perceived CSR reflect the perception of an employee about the discretionary actions of their organization's plan to improve and enhance the well-being of their stakeholders (as well as their natural environment). Originate on social identity theory, this study proposes that perception of employees of CSR activities can positively affect their beliefs about the status and reputation of their organization, thus nurturing their pride of being the member of their organization and willingness to rejoice in its reflected prestige through an upgrade level of organizational identification. Furthermore, some studies revealed that initiatives of CSR can depict the standards of an organization (Becker-Olsen et al., 2006; Bhattacharya et al., 2009; Bibi & Ali, 2021; Sulehri et al., 2022). Also when employees perceived CSR, they feel that they have physical, affecting and cognitive resources to engage more personally with their work role and identify the value and external prestige of their organization. Companies are often seen as prestigious, who considers themselves socially and environmentally responsible (Glavas and Godwin 2013; Shahid & Ali, 2015; Shahbaz et al., 2015), and employees of such firms are also well aware of their actions while performing work duties. Many previous research studies have shown significant association between perceived CSR and organization identification. Employees are more likely to develop a more strong bond with their organizations, when knowing that their organization holds a favorable prestige (favorable public image or good reputation) as part of their connection. According to M Mozes, Z josman (2011) research' indicates employees feel more proud to identify with the positive and good reputation of their organization, hence demonstrated a positive association between perceived CSR and organization identification. SH Ko, WM Hur (2018) also illustrated positive connection between perceived CSR and OID. Q Tian, JL Robertson (2019) predicted positive correlation among perceived CSR and organization identification.

2.2. Transformational Identification

Transformational leadership promotes follower's concerns for achievements, attainment, self-actualization and wellbeing of others. Transformational leadership deemed to encourage employee behaviors that escalate above their personal interest (Carlson and Perrewe, 1995; Satti et al., 2013; Siddiqi et al., 2014; Senturk & Ali, 2022). Researchers expound that a transformational leader has positive and unique way of explaining things, which ultimately linked to a extensive variety of positive work outcomes as well as fosters positive behavior among followers. Leaders play a fundamental role in supporting and encouraging individual initiatives which leads to improved work procedures and outcomes for the benefit and betterment of the organization. Generally, transformational leaders are positive influencers with truthful self-concepts who help and support openness among followers which translates into better work outcomes. Thus, transformational leadership fosters positive identity of their organizations among followers.

2.3. Perceived Organizational Support

Perceived organizational support referred to the global belief of employees concerning the amount to which the organization care about their wellbeing and value their contribution. Perceived organizational support also be define as the support given to individual by their organization in order to develop confidence and sense of responsibility. POS is one of the important ways to understand and evaluate employees and also viewed as basic framework to identify the relationship between employees and their organization. POS is notion that considers the favorable outcomes of employees. Previous researches illustrated the relationship between POS and organizational identification. When organization trusts and appreciates their employees' enhances the feeling of being valued and realized by the organization (POS) and boots self-confidence among employees. The involvement by organizations developed skills of self enhancement in employees and thus there is a more strong motivation and relation to identify with the organization. Hence, it develops the organization-based collective identity.

2.4. Organizational Identification

Organization identification refers to the degree to which an employee identifies him or herself by the same symbols and attributes that they believe define their organization. When the employee perceives external image of organization this develops a desire in employee to grow with it by enhancing their self-esteem and self-actualization. Therefore, when the perception of an employee about their organization and perception of outsiders (external image of organization) improve, they view their organizational external image as more appealing and attractive and feel proud to identify with their organization (Dutton et al., 1994). Socially responsible and pro environmental corporations are considered to have great value in the eyes of external and internal stakeholders as compared to those nonsocial and irresponsible organizations towards the environment. Stakeholders and stockholders in market virtually identify the reflection of distinction organizations. Thus, employees feel more proud to match their values with their organizations values and proudly consider themselves to be the part of such reputable and well-known organization. Previous studies have shown positive relationship of organizational identification and employee pro environmental behavior. Such as T Islam, H Asad (2019), proved the positive association of organizational identification with pro environmental behavior. Another research by S Cheema, BM Al-Ghazali (2020) mentioned significant relationship of organizational identification.

2.5. Pro environmental Behavior

Organizations around the world are stepping toward the ways with aim to recover their environmental performance by persuading their employees to connect in activities and tasks that help enhancing deliberate pro environmental behavior among employees (Robertson and Barling 2017). To keeping up with the trend organizations has started working on organizational environmental policy with the intend to improve employee perception of environment and associated pro environmental behavior in work settings, the responsibility of environmental policies and practices considered as keys predecessor to the social and environmentally responsible behavior of employees. Q. Tian, Robertson (2019) demonstrated predictors that influence pro environmental behavior among employee, which include perceived corporate social responsibility, and organizational identification significantly influences pro environmental behavior in employees. Pro environmental behavior define as a kind of behavior at workplace that is reliable with a firm's environmentally and socially responsible objectives and values by enhancing welfare of external stakeholder (e.g., the natural environment), and that contributes to the success of organization (Boiral 2009; Norton et al. 2015). One of an important part for an organization to achieve sustainable environmental development is employee's pro environmental behavior (Ones & Dilchert, 2012). Employee pro environmental behavior is considered more valuable, because it is linked to organizational change and leads to environmental improvements (B Afsar, S Cheema, F Javed 2018).

Hypothesis 1: *Employees' perceptions of CSR are positively related to organizational identification*

Hypothesis 2: *Transformational leader practices will support stronger organizational identification.*

Hypothesis 3: *Transformational leadership positively influences organizational identification*

Hypothesis 4: *Perceived organizational support is positively related to OID*

Hypothesis 5: *Perceived organizational support should be positively associated with organizational identification.*

Hypothesis 6: *There is a positive relation between organizational identification and pro-environmental behavior.*

Hypothesis 7: *Organization Identification is positively associated with pro environmental behavior.*

Figure-1

3. Empirical Review

S Bose, B Patnaik, S Mohanty (2020) examined the link between transformational leadership and organizational identification with the mediation of psychological empowerment. Data were gathered from 199 respondents working in IT sector and analyzed using SPSS and structural equation modeling technique. Results are showing positive association of transformational leadership with organizational identification and psychological empowerment. Also, psychological empowerment mediates the relationship of transformational leadership and organizational identification. The study concludes that empowerment plays an important part in the success of any organization. Also, this study reveals that psychological empowerment and transformational leadership encourage and motivate employees to perform better and inspire higher level of organizational identification. Bindu Chhabra (2020) examined the relationship between perceived organizational support (POS) and positive reciprocity beliefs (PRB) with organizational identification (OID). Data were gathered from 308 respondents from different types of organization and analyzed by using Hierarchical multiple regression modeling technique. Results revealed positive correlations between POS and OID and this positive relation moderated by PRB. It is concluded that POS and OID is supposed to stronger for those employees with having stronger positive reciprocity beliefs.

B Afsar, BM Al-Ghazali (2020) explored how perceived CSR effects pro environmental behavior with impact of organizational identification, environmental consciousness and entrepreneurship. Data was collected from 122 managers and 479 employees from hospitality industry and has been analyzed by using Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA). Study illustrated that perceived CSR is positively relates with employee pro environmental behavior with the mediating effect of OID and moderating effects of entrepreneurship and environmental consciousness. This study has explained organizations that aims to promote pro-environmental behavior in their workplace needs to address the issue related to individual level factors such as employee environmental consciousness towards the environment and they must create environmental enablers such as CSR or corporate entrepreneurship or organizational identification so that employee become more conscious for the environment.

Q. Tian, J. L. Robertson (2019) conducted research to explore the relationship between voluntary pro environmental behavior and perceived corporate social responsibility. The data was collected by 183 respondents from casinos and hospitality industry. Results in the proposed model had significant association of perceived CSR with pro environmental behavior but shown an indirect association of perceived CSR with pro environmental behavior through mediating variable organizational identification with moderated effect of empathy. According to the findings of the study, it can be concluded that perceived CSR directly encourages voluntary pro environmental behavior in employees.

X Peng, S Lee, Z Lu (2020) explored the impact of perceived job performance and organizational identification on employee pro environmental behavior. Data was collected from 829 employees from Chinese hotel industry. The data was than analyzed by using ordinary least square (OLS) regression analysis. This study has illustrated positive relationship of perceived job performance with organizational identification and positive association of organizational identification with employee pro environmental behavior. This study concluded that organizational identification is an important predictor of employee pro environmental behavior.

S Cheema, B Afsar (2019) examined the relationship between employee perception of CSR and organization citizenship behavior with mediating effect of organizational identification and environmental orientation fit. With the help of 374 respondents and structural equation modeling had been used to analyze their relationship. Results revealed employee's perception of CSR positively associated with OCB and positive relationship between OID and OCB also illustrated that OID and environmental orientation fit mediated the effects of perceived CSR on OCB. As this study did not control for particular type of industry and company it is suggested, future research

should consider a type of industry and then reveal individual work outcomes by using these variables in that industry.

4. Methodology

The purpose of this research study is to examine the association between perceived CSR, transformational leadership and perceived organizational support with organizational identification and pro environmental behavior. This research is correlational because the purpose of this study is to analyze the factors mentioned above. Research approaches are of three types that include quantitative research approach, qualitative research approach and also pragmatic research approach (mixed method). This research is a complete quantitative based research. As in quantitative approach researchers are permit to generalize the population of the study, which considers a key drawback in qualitative approach. Generally purpose of research can be descriptive, exploratory and explanatory in nature. Descriptive (this research is more detailed and describes the features of phenomenon or population that are being considered, and purpose of this study is analyze the gap and expanding the level of understanding of readers). Exploratory (exploring a fresh research, new angle or new topic which is not studied, the main agenda of this research attempts to initiate the ground work which will lead to future researches). Explanatory (research that is previously conducted but have some lacking in it and now the new research will be conducted on the same phenomena). In this study used explanatory research purpose. Sampling design consist of target population and sampling techniques with the estimated sample size. This study, have used convenience sampling to make sample on the basis of accessibility and convenience. This study used non-probability sampling technique because it is time and cost saving also this technique gives efficient results which can be generalized for the whole population.

5. Data Analysis and Discussions

5.1. Measurement Model

Figure-2

Measurement model of this study has been developed using Smart PLS (version 3.3.2). As Smart-PLS offers wide range of potential for researchers, the use of Smart-PLS is increasing in many business disciplines such as marketing and management studies, one of the main advantages of using Smart-PLS is that it works very readily with much smaller and larger samples (JF Hair, CM Ringle, Sarstedt, 2011). The purpose of using Smart-PLS in this study is to create the relationship between the latent and observed variables. We evaluated discriminant validity, convergent validity and reliability of perceived CSR, transformational leadership, perceived organizational support, organizational identification and employee pro environmental behavior. Table 1 demonstrates the outer loading for each indicator, here the result of outer loading shows values that are in excess of 0.708 which indicates the accurate relationship among the items with their latent constructs (Hair Jr, Hult, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2017). This study estimated construct reliability and convergent validity for each variable by using composite reliability (CR) and average variance extracted (AVE). Values of AVE are greater than 0.5 (Hair et al., 2019), similarly values of roh_A and CR were greater than the criterion values that is 0.70. These values

suggested that there is good internal validity and construct reliability in all five variables. Moreover, value of Cronbach alpha for each of five variables is greater than 0.70 which shows that there is good internal construct reliability.

Table 1: Measurement Model (n=208)

Latent Construct	Indicators	Loadings	Alpha	rho_A	CR	AVE
Organizational Identification			0.906	0.906	0.927	0.681
	oi1	0.804				
	oi2	0.822				
	oi3	0.850				
	oi4	0.825				
	oi5	0.876				
Perceived CSR	oi6	0.769				
			0.860	0.870	0.900	0.643
	pcsr2	0.777				
	pcsr3	0.860				
	pcsr4	0.849				
	pcsr5	0.731				
Employee Pro-environmental Behavior	pcsr6	0.785				
			0.859	0.869	0.898	0.639
	peb1	0.838				
	peb2	0.852				
	peb3	0.746				
	peb4	0.771				
Perceived Organizational Support	peb6	0.786				
			0.897	0.900	0.921	0.660
	pos1	0.776				
	pos2	0.809				
	pos3	0.829				
	pos4	0.836				
Transformational Leadership	pos5	0.829				
	pos6	0.794				
			0.875	0.877	0.906	0.618
	tfl1	0.716				
	tfl2	0.778				
	tfl3	0.868				
tfl4	0.814					
tfl5	0.767					
tfl6	0.766					

Notes: CR= Composite Reliability; AVE= Average Variance Extracted.

After convergent validity and reliability, this study determines the discriminant validity for the proposed model. In evaluating process of discriminant validity, first step is to check the cross loadings after cross loading we assess HTMT matrices. As suggested by the values of loading must be greater than 0.5 or ideally 0.7 (Hair et al., 2019). The results of cross loadings of this study are presented in table 2. It is evident that values of all indicators are greater than 0.7, which means that loadings of each indicator are strongly associated with their constructs.

In addition, in estimating procedure of HTMT ratios, this study assess the HTMT values via the PLS algorithm method. The results obtained from HTMT ratio were significantly lower than 1. Suggesting all the latent constructs has establishes the discriminant validity. The results of HTMT matrices suggested that discriminant validity was attained at 0.90, that means all the values for inter construct ratios are below 0.90 as shown below. Table 3 shows the results of HTMT ratios. As suggested by Henseler et al., (2015) higher values than 0.9 of HTMT matrice indicates problem for discriminant validity. In table 3 the values of HTMT for this study are less than 0.9, which indicates the results are statistically significant. And discriminant validity is established.

Table 2: Discriminant Validity- Cross loadings

	Employee Pro-environmental behavior	Organizational Identification	Perceived CSR	Perceived organizational support	Transformational Leadership
oi1	0.552	0.804	0.449	0.542	0.567
oi2	0.508	0.822	0.421	0.537	0.557
oi3	0.487	0.850	0.418	0.583	0.592
oi4	0.494	0.825	0.448	0.604	0.603
oi5	0.603	0.876	0.451	0.535	0.522
oi6	0.641	0.769	0.474	0.404	0.441
pcsr2	0.422	0.443	0.777	0.411	0.500
pcsr3	0.498	0.501	0.860	0.521	0.504
pcsr4	0.472	0.435	0.849	0.454	0.511
pcsr5	0.377	0.351	0.731	0.410	0.470
pcsr6	0.428	0.408	0.785	0.507	0.548
peb1	0.838	0.601	0.486	0.505	0.520
peb2	0.852	0.548	0.513	0.484	0.563
peb3	0.746	0.400	0.344	0.387	0.426
peb4	0.771	0.496	0.379	0.341	0.448
peb6	0.786	0.576	0.455	0.425	0.492
pos1	0.447	0.490	0.472	0.776	0.634
pos2	0.440	0.509	0.436	0.809	0.686
pos3	0.487	0.576	0.492	0.829	0.666
pos4	0.408	0.465	0.493	0.836	0.614
pos5	0.404	0.498	0.467	0.829	0.620
pos6	0.438	0.593	0.448	0.794	0.641
tfl1	0.506	0.526	0.560	0.501	0.716
tfl2	0.450	0.491	0.431	0.525	0.778
tfl3	0.547	0.548	0.535	0.688	0.868
tfl4	0.529	0.548	0.554	0.715	0.814
tfl5	0.451	0.516	0.450	0.624	0.767
tfl6	0.412	0.492	0.429	0.681	0.766

Table 3: Discriminant validity- HTMT

	Employee Pro-environmental behavior	Organizational Identification	Perceived CSR	Perceived organizational support	Transformational Leadership
Employee Pro-environmental behavior					
Organizational Identification	0.742				
Perceived CSR	0.630	0.605			
Perceived organizational support	0.608	0.713	0.655		
Transformational Leadership	0.705	0.745	0.726	0.893	

5.2. Hypothesis Testing

Basic purpose of this research under focus was to observe the direct relationship of independent variables (perceived CSR, transformational leadership and perceived organizational support) with the intervening variable (organizational identification) and also the relationship of intervening variable (organizational identification) with dependent variable (pro environmental behavior), secondly evaluating the hypothesized relationships among the constructs through a structural model. For testing hypothesis, this study used smart PLS, the technique of PLS algorithm used to assess the relationship among the variables. To develop hypothesis we have resample the data using 5000 complete bootstrapping. The results of hypothesis are illustrated in the tables given below. Direct effects of variables are demonstrated in table 4.

In Table 5, we have examined the coefficient of determination and blindfolding for the proposed model. As recommended by Hair et al (2019), the greater the values of R-square and adjusted R-square are considered to be

significant and substantial. Here we can see the significant results of R-square and adjusted R-square, as the results showing value greater than 0.25. According to Hair et al. (2019), to estimate the predictive power of model, blindfolding technique is used. As per the guidance of Stone (1974) and Geisser (1974), Q square can be used to assess the predictive power relevance of the measurement model. In this study we have use the technique of blindfolding by using Smart PLS and Table 5 illustrates the estimated values of outcome variables are greater than zero, this indicates the predictive accuracy of the model is acceptable.

Table 4: Direct Effects (n=208)

Hypothesis	Estimate	STDEV	T Statistics	P Values	Decision
Perceived CSR -> Organizational Identification	0.162	0.073	2.232	0.026	Supported
Transformational Leadership -> Organizational Identification	0.326	0.105	3.107	0.002	Supported
Perceived organizational support -> Organizational Identification	0.296	0.093	3.191	0.001	Supported
Organizational Identification -> Employee Pro-environmental behavior	0.665	0.067	9.885	0.000	Supported

Table 5: Path Analysis and Blind Folding

	R2	R2 adjusted	Q2
Employee Pro-environmental behavior	0.442	0.439	0.270
Organizational Identification	0.495	0.488	0.328

6. Discussion

The findings of this study indicate a significant relationship between the predictive variables and outcome variables. Considering the benefits of employee behavior towards environmental issues and the enhancement of organizational identification, the major purpose of this research was to analyze and estimate the effect of perceived CSR, transformational leadership, and perceived organizational support on organizational identification and employee pro-environmental behavior. The first research objective was to analyze the impact of perceived CSR by employees on organizational identification. Findings of research indicated that perceived CSR is positively and significantly associated with organizational identification. Implementation of CSR policies can be beneficial for organizations. The majority of respondents in this study are graduates and work in well-reputed pharmaceutical industries, and they agreed that participation in CSR activities by their organization enhances their level of identification with their organizations. 50.9% of male respondents and 48.1% of female respondents are in support of the implementation of CSR policy. The findings and results of this study have been found consistent with other previous studies as well (S Cheema, B Afsar, 2019 and K De Roeck, 2016) as the findings of this study highlight that when an organization implements CSR policy on employees, employees relate more positively with their organizations and promote a positive corporate image of the organization. So, when an employee perceives that their organization is socially responsible, so employees feel more proud and are happier to identify themselves with their organization, which translates into more environmentally friendly behavior (Q. Tian, J. L. Robertson, 2019). Most of the respondents in this study are working as subordinates in their respected firms, and responses gathered suggested that the influence of transformational leaders on their subordinates matters a lot. When supervisors and leaders possess qualities of transformational leadership, then subordinates become more motivated and feel good to identify themselves with their organizations. The results of this current study have been found consistent with previous researches (Bindu Chhabra, 2020) and (Y Shen, T Jackson, 2014) that when employees feel central and valued, included, and respected, this leads to employees' stronger belief in involvement by their organization, which is self-enhancing and attractive for them. Thus, employees are more motivated to identify with their respected organization.

Furthermore, when employees perceive trust and value (POS) from their organizations, this tends to increase the trust level of employees with their organization and also enhance identification level and relationship with their organization (H He, HQ Pham, 2014). Evidently, employees value their organizations more when they perceive organizational support and appreciation (LW Lam, 2016). Organizations must value the contribution and wellbeing of their employees to increase organizational identification. And when employees perceive organizational support, they tend to relate and identify more with their organizations, which in return increases the trust level from both sides. Evidently, organizational identification likely to increase employee pro-environmental behavior, and results of this research have been found consistent with previous researches as well (Q. Tian, J. L. Robertson, 2019; B Afsar, S Cheema, 2018). When an employee estimates their worth with the social image of their respected organization, and they perceive that their organization is environmentally responsible as well as socially responsible, they probably like to identify strongly with their organizations, such factors influence employees to

perform voluntary environmental activities for their organizations. So the employee displays more pro-environmental behavior (B Afsar, BM Al-Ghazali, 2020).

7. Conclusion

This study demonstrated that perception of employees about the involvement by their organizations in environmental related social and corporate responsibilities translates into organization promoting their employees pro environmental behavior. Based on the findings of the existing study, it is concluded that managers need to develop CSR policy and promote the influence of transformational leaders, as to encourage the level of organizational identification and employee pro environmental behavior. It is also evident that when employee perceives support from their organization they relate more with their organizations hence results in higher organization identification which reciprocates more voluntary pro environmental behavior from employees

7.1. Managerial Implications

Based on the above results and findings of the present study, organizations that like to promote voluntary environmental behavior among their employees must address some basic issues so that employees voluntarily perform the environmental tasks. It is evident from the findings that employee obliged to perform voluntarily environmental behavior when they perceived organizational support as well as influence of transformational leaders play an important part in the same process. This also helps in implications of CSR policies which ultimately results in higher level of organizational identification

7.2. Recommendations and future direction

According to the findings of this study, to increase environmental awareness among employees, organizations must consider the steps which exhibits the pro environmental behavior of their employees. One of the findings of this research suggests that there is a broad scope of implementing CSR policy in any organization, because when employee perceives that organization implementing the CSR activities and behaving in environmental friendly manner they are obliged to do the same. And as perceive CSR is positively and significantly related to organizational identification, this relationship triggers pro environmental behavior of employees. Also this research recommend that organizations need more transformational leaders that foster the self-motivation and positivity among the employees so that relationship between the organization and employee improves, thus employees feel more happy to identify with their organization and behave more in environmental friendly ways. Organizational support should be given more importance in the context of promoting level of identification of an employee with their organization. Because when an employee perceives that their contributions are valued by their organizations they become self-motivated and also it is beneficial for organizations in order to retain their employees. Thus, employees voluntarily perform more environmental tasks and this influence pro environmental behavior of employees working in any industrial sector. This study has certain limitation like any other research. Firstly, collection of data was done from pharmaceutical industries of Pakistan as well as convenience sampling technique is used. In order to collect data from the target population, future studies can be conducted with this same research model by using random techniques of sampling. Secondly, this study gathered the data from only HR firms for the purpose of generalizability of results. Future researches can consider sample from employees working in other sectors and cultures to examine the results using the same research model for wider generalizability. The same model can also be investigated in other industrial sectors and counties other than Pakistan. Future researcher can consider other methods as well that is qualitative or mix method, to examine pro environmental behavior of employees working in Pakistan.

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